

Module 7	Introduction to Statistical Data Analysis and Machine Learning (SDA&ML)
Course coordinator	Matteo Biagetti (MB)
Lecturers	Tommaso Rodani and MB
Class duration	24 hours
Module description	This module will focus on a variety of techniques and tools for the statistical analysis of data and meta-data for parameter inference, pattern recognition, model fitting and comparison. The module is split into two main parts: an introduction to probability theory and statistics, and an introduction to machine learning and neural networks. Each topic is introduced with a hands-on approach, with plenty of practical examples and exercises.
Main topics	<p>Introduction to probability theory and statistic: elements of probability theory, sampling and sampling distributions, point and interval estimation, hypothesis testing, chi-square test, nonparametric methods, elements of Bayesian inference Model fitting and comparison</p> <p>Introduction to Machine Learning and Neural Networks Linear methods for regression and classification Kernel methods for regression and classification Learning with imbalanced/missing data Hyperparameter tuning, cross validation Data intrinsic dimension and dimensionality reduction techniques Clustering methods Elements of deep learning</p>
Objectives	On completion of this module students should have learnt how to use a basic set of algorithms and tools for analyzing data in their laboratory. They can devise several techniques to 1) extract information/infer parameters, 2) recognize unknown/known patterns, 3) fit theoretical or empirical models, 4) solve simple regression or classification tasks using machine learning algorithms, from a dataset and/or its metadata.
References	Books: - 'Pattern Recognition and Machine Learning', C. Bishop - 'An introduction to Statistical Learning' G. James, D. Witten, T. Hastie, R. Tibshirani -'The elements of statistical learning' T. Hastie, R. Tibshirani, J. Friedman -'Deep learning with Python', F. Chollet Other references: - https://www.biophys.mpg.de/2139320/statistical-data-analysis - https://ocw.mit.edu/courses/15-075j-statistical-thinking-and-dataanalysis-fall-2011/pages/lecture-notes/ - https://people.sc.fsu.edu/~sshanbhag/Cowan_Statistics.pdf